

ABOUT CONDITIONS

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The seemingly arbitrary traces of nature growing in-between two buildings, the transient density of a fog, the unstable logic of the course of the Mississippi river, the controlled humidity in a botanical greenhouse.

Can architecture focus
on what is ephemeral and
generate similar condi-
tions?

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Truwant + Rodet +, Naturgemälde, Lasting Long, Coming Soon, CH-Basel, 2019

Like most of today's monuments, the Münster Cathedral in Basel appears mostly as an idealized collective memory depicted without its context, like a landmark in a snowball. But the real history of the 1000 years old cathedral is linked to its geomorphological condition. Historically the Rhine used to flow straight between today's Grenzach-Wyhlen and Weil am Rhine.

But during the last glacial period the enormous rubbles and gravel deposits of the Feldberg glacier were transported down the Wiese forming a wide delta and forcing a bend in the riverbed of the Rhine. Carved out by the river and the accumulated sediments, the Münster plateau naturally arose on the southern bank. Its specific morphology became a major asset for the Celts and the Romans who sought to settle along the course of this important navigable waterway. It offered a strategic vantage point 40m above the water level, ideal to erect in first instance an oppidum for control and defensive purposes, and later on a cathedral as a demonstration of religious power.

The proposed image is an imagined cross section through its bigger context, revealing exciting geographical, geological and cultural clues informing us about all its ecosystems, historical layers and even potential futures.

The cathedral is a small element in a web of interrelations and stories. Without the river bend of the Rhine, there would be no settlement, no defense, no power, no Münster, no pontifical council, no university, no research, no chemistry, no ...

Since the Industrial Revolution western civilizations have tried to control the environment with the objective of turning it into productive resources. Architecture is at the core of this transformation. And as a result, our landscapes have turned into a continuous carpet of settlements, networks of roads, commercial sheds, polluted soils, displaced fauna, disrupted flora, predicting a future of natural disasters and social distress.

Today, in the midst of this ecological crisis this shift cannot be denied anymore. And though we begin to see the consequences of centuries of abuse, the approach to architecture isn't changing and remains self-centered. This act of domination will persist as long as we keep on referring to architecture as "buildings" and relegating landscape, public space, service spaces, interstitial spaces, infrastructure, etc. to the background.

The classical practice of architecture is inadequate to tackle our contemporary condition: that of an ultra-complex urban, political, social, ecological structure where the boundaries between disciplines are no longer clearly pronounced. A condition that requires a non-discriminatory, non-segregationally, non-compartmental attitude. A mindset where one accepts dissolution, vagueness, informality, hybridity, fauna, and flora. An approach that accepts that everything is part of the same environment.

Complex systems & Naturgemälde

The contemporary understanding of the interrelationships between society, nature and politics found its origin in the work of the Prussian scientist and visionary thinker Alexander von Humboldt. He is seen as one of the last Homo Universalis, who was living in the 19th century, during the heydays of the industrialization, at a moment where ironically all disciplines were encouraged to become hyper-specialized.

But Von Humboldt had an interest for the whole world around him and this unsatisfiable curiosity drove him on extreme excursions to the mountain ranges of Europe, Latin America, Russia and the United States of America. During these travels, he started to organize plants according to their altitude and climate. He concluded that the flora from different locations but similar height were comparable. This finding helped him to understand that everything was linked and that there is a “unity in variety”¹. But his recognition of the whole world as one complex eco-system went much further than understanding its botanical interconnections. His interest in economic, political and social conditions made him see the effect of human behavior on the environment. He connected for example, very early-on, the negative influence of colonialism and slavery on ecosystems and predicted the devastating consequences of deforestation on future generations.

Alexander von Humboldt understood the world as a web of connections and he was at the origin of the definition of ecology as “the study of the interrelationships of organisms with their environment and each other”²

The extensive reports of his travels made him one of the most influential people of his time. And probably as important as his findings were the numerous illustrations of ecosystems in his renowned publications. In 1802, during his five year-long exploration of the Andes which was crucial in the shaping of his perception of the world, Alexander von Humboldt started to draw his first Naturgemälde, trying to translate a “micro cosmos on one page”³. The 54 cm by 84 cm drawing *Ein Naturgemälde der Anden* that is based on the Chimborazo sketches shows a cross-section of the volcano, linking altitude with flora, temperature, gravity, humidity.

Later on, Von Humboldt developed together with a set of artists his paintings of nature in which infographics were used for the first time to show these interrelationships and made his theories understandable for a much bigger audience. The Naturgemälde became a crucial tool in the understanding of ephemeral conditions, invisible correlations, and transcontinental connections.

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Juliette Villechange, Maya Mouttapa, Theophane Lefebvre Delean, Analysis of the fountain of Meret Oppenheim, Ensav, FR-Versailles, Studio Truwant + Rodet +, Spring Semester 20

In 1983, a modernistic looking concrete fountain was erected on Waisenhausplatz in Bern. But in that year, the column-like sculpture by Meret Oppenheim didn't reach it's final form yet. The artist had just put the perfect conditions in place so the calcareous water from the Bernese mountains could leave a tuff deposit on the structure. This new rocky landscape becomes the perfect base for a vertical wild garden of mosses and wild grasses whose seeds are carried along by the wind.

The simple structure put in place by Meret Oppenheim, reveals a whole existing ecological system. It creates a dynamic sculpture that is never finished and that connects the city to its surrounding landscape.

During the spring semester of 2020, our studio at the Ensav was focussing on the topic of Uncertain Conditions. The students analysed projects that dealt with concepts like Liquid space, Time as material, Climate, Habitat, and Nature & Technology. The drawings of Alexander von Humboldt served as a starting point to represent the ephemeral and to illustrate the processes used by for example Meret Oppenheim.

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Proposals for uncertain conditions

Rather than viewing architecture as an authoritarian discipline that produces fixed and hermetic objects, we, Truwant + Rodet +, would like to think of our field of study in the light of Humboldt's work as part of a bigger complex system. In our work and practice, we define architecture as a more fluid and transversal discipline, lifting the separations between landscape, structure, art, science, territory, technology, biology, botanism.

Architecture as a generator of potentials and conditions could be regarded as a living organism or what one could call an adaptive system similar to a colony of ants, the stock exchange, users of a library or even the development of a construction site. All involve a dynamic network of entities and actors whose behavior and retroaction cannot be predicted. Architecture could have a pulse, a rhythm, could grow, or dissolve following unpredictable parameters. Architecture could be made interdependent with the context, temperature, humidity, light, fauna and flora.

This ambition is translated in many of the projects of Truwant + Rodet + by means of programmatic, spatial, technological and material manipulation with the aim of blurring limits between the built mass and its surroundings, allowing for spatial fluidity between inside and outside. Our search for a "Liquid Space" becomes an investigation on thresholds as a space of potential, that can be stretched, pierced or dissolved, to generate new conditions for acoustic, thermal, visual, political and social exchanges.

The threshold not as a limit in classical conception, but as a transitional space that articulates interior/exterior, landscape/building, urban/rural, natural/artificial.

Following the concepts of von Humboldts researches, the question arises if architecture, like nature, can be conducive to evolution and transformation over time? Time can become a design tool within the practice. Planning the rules and conditions for a project, becomes a bigger priority then searching for a final form.

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Truwant + Rodet + Bruther + Carlotta Daro + Laurent Stalder +, proposal for the French Pavilion, IT-Venice, 2017

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The project for the Venice Biennale 2018 proposes an update of the French Pavilion through a transformation that involves 3 types of long-term interventions: the integration of the outside spaces in the spatial organisation of the pavilion, the articulation of the thresholds through a series of openings, the transformation of the pavilion from a static and hierarchical architecture into a dynamic and interactive device provided with technical equipment adapted to the current requirements of its programming. The project aims not only at transforming the pavilion to match the contemporary needs of the Biennale, but also at showing the spatial, constructive and atmospheric, and thus aesthetic, potential of the architecture.

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Truwant + Rodet + Oxara +, proposal for a transformative courtyard, CH-SION, 2020

A hidden courtyard in a new public building is cut off from its direct surroundings and presented in the competition brief as an empty piece of land. But when located in its bigger context, the courtyard becomes part of the Delta of the Bramois river.

Truwant + Rodet + proposes to use the different types of soil along the river as raw material for a set of cement-free concrete tiles, a method developed by Oxara. The different treatments of the tiles will determine the longevity of the concrete, foreseeing a possible decay of parts of the courtyards. With the dissolving of certain tiles, seeds will come to the surface, creating a transformative garden, that will create a very specific piece of nature, grown out of its context. The project sets in place a set of conditions that in time will shape the appearance and evolution of the courtyard.

To project is represented in one panel that combines, like Alexander von Humboldts Naturgemälde, infographics with sections and plans, representing simultaneously the existing conditions like climat, wind,... and the projected conditions that script a possible future.

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principe colorimétrique de répartition des dalles

dalles cuites et traitées

dalles semi-cuite et non cuite qui se dissoudrons dans le temps

enseillement en été de 07:15 à 19:15

enseillement en hiver de 09:30 à 15:30

topographie

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Truwant + Rodet + Hilbert +, Flexible Structures, CH-Basel, 2021

The transformation of a shop into an office space demands an update of the technical equipment that control the spatial conditions.

By removing the fake ceiling, the structure of the building and its history are revealed. The structure is painted in a strong green and links the accidental space back to the bigger building. The existing ventilation system is adapted to the new demands. The existing metal beams are wrapped for fireprotection. New curtain rails give the possibility to divide and darken the space. An new grid of lightning links the front and the back and can create contrasting atmospheres in separate zones.

The whole spatial intervention is reduced to the ceiling. An image composed out of a big amount of pictures of the ceiling shows the overlapping layers that control the spatial and atmospheric conditions. The ceiling functions as a 5th facade.

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Truwant + Rodet + Hilbert +, Strange Encounters, CH-Basel, 2020

The brief for the transformation of a one-family house, can be summarized to 3 topics: the renewal of the heating system, a new staircase that resolves the connection with an first renovation that happened in the 80's and a structural element that makes it possible to organize an open floor plan.

The 3 new elements are combined in one central element that becomes the center of the house, a strange hybrid between heating, circulation and structure. The new element ties together the previous renovations of the house, forming a new whole.

A collaged image combines the planned future of the project (a render), a ruin of the past (the building site), together with an axonometry of the new intervention and proposes that the new renovation is another intermediate state of a house that keeps on transforming with every new owner.

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Berghaus, Heinrich Karl Wilhelm: Dr. Heinrich Berghaus' physikalischer Atlas : eine, unter der fördernden Anregung Alexander's von Humboldt verfasste, Sammlung von 93 Karten, auf denen die hauptsächlichsten Erscheinungen der anorganischen [...]. Gotha : Verlag von Justus Perthes, 1852. ETH-Bibliothek Zürich, Rar KA 52, <https://doi.org/10.3931/e-rara-68876> / Public Domain Mark

Modes of representation

What is the role of the drawing in this shift of perception? In order to instigate new proposals, it is necessary to challenge our communication means to translate movement, time, blurriness & climatic conditions. It was through the use of his *Naturgemälde* as a research tool that von Humboldt managed to develop and communicate his understanding of the world as complex ecological system.

Colours and arrows translate temperature and wind speed, but the beauty of Humboldt's pictorial proposals is the capacity to encapsulate all of it in one image. Within our practice, we are exploring how we can visualize these ephemeral qualities through the combination and overlapping of different media. Uncertainty, vagueness and lack of control provide design opportunities. A project image can combine renders with pictures of the building site and a technical drawing. A collage can become a representation of an imagined past and a possible future. Or a plan can be simultaneously an axonometrie that shows only phenomenological qualities while abandoning every representation of form.

And like learning from von Humboldt and his *Naturgemälde*, architecture could look at contemporary scientific research to find new tools in an ever-growing challenge of revealing and depicting complexity. Seeing the new composite images from NASA, that combine x-ray and infrared data, offering an incredible spectacle of explosions gas emissions and radiation, yet invisible to humans, helps us to visualize and to understand the complex systems in which we live.

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The Pillars of Creation in the Eagle Nebula taken by the Hubble telescope in 1995, NASA, Jeff Hester, and Paul Scowen (Arizona State University)

In 2014 Nasa revisited one of their most popular images, the Pillars of Creation, representing “three giant columns of cold gas bathed in the scorching ultraviolet light from a cluster of young, massive stars in a small region of the Eagle Nebula, or M16.”

Although the image has a photorealistic quality, it actually combines different views (near-infrared as well as visible light) into one image. “The blue colors in the image represent oxygen, red is sulfur, and green represents both nitrogen and hydrogen.”⁵ Introducing a natural phenomena to a wider audience.

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